

RAINFALL EFFECTS ON WATER USE AND YIELD OF COCOA IN NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

Weather hazards pose considerable danger to cash crops production, farmers suffers major loses in income due to the poor yield associated with the weather problems. This study examined the effects of rainfall on water use and yield of cocoa in Nigeria and other variables such as producer prices, exchange rate and level of national income (GDP). The effect of total rainfall, producer prices, exchange rate and GDP on the yields of Cocoa was estimated for the period 1970-2003 in Nigeria. The methods of analysis employed in the study were mainly error-correction model (ECM) within the context of co-integration theory. Also, results showed that all the variables are not stationary at their levels and thus, a need for differencing once to attain stationarity. Statistical significance of the error-correction terms for the yield validates the existence of an equilibrium relationship among the variables in each of these co-integrating vectors. However, rainfall, producer price, and GDP were the most significant factors influencing the yield of cocoa. Efforts to boost the production of cocoa will need to incorporate policy measures to improve producer prices, address the problem of global warming and create enabling environment for local industries and income redistribution for all and sundry that would increased country's GDP.

KEYWORDS: Cocoa, Rainfall, Nigeria, cointegration and error correction mechanism.

INTRODUCTION

Agricultural production makes use of natural and man-made resources. Natural resources include land, water, air and soil conditions, while man-made resources are supplied and influenced by man. They include labour, capital management or entrepreneurs. Among the natural resources, Climate is the predominant factor. Climate means the habitual state and behaviour that covers the atmospheric condition of location at a particular time. Weather is often associated with annual yields conditions whereas climate is associated with the type and geographical extent of crops that can be grown. According to Wittier (1995), "Climate and weather can be proclaimed as the most important determining factors for both plant growth and crop productivity." Climate change is casting a cloud of uncertainty over the future of agriculture, the mainstay of the African economy (Obasi, 1997).

The climate of Nigeria strides from a very wet coastal area with annual rainfall greater than 3500mm to the Sahel region in the north-western and north- eastern parts with annual rainfall less than 600mm. The inter-annual variability of rainfall, particularly in the northern parts is largely, often result in climate hazards, especially floods and droughts with their devastating effects on food production and associated calamities and sufferings. More often than not certain parts of Nigeria receive less than 75 per cent of their annual rainfall and this is particularly worrisome in Northern part of Nigeria.

Weather and climate influence most of the processes involved in crop production for example: solar radiation produces energy for warming the soil, plants and for metabolic processes, rainfall and its characteristics in terms of amount of intensity, reliability and distribution influence crop growth and soil erosion. Atmospheric evaporation determines the performance and survival of crops. Planting and dates are determines by the start of rains. Rainfall determines the vegetation cover of a particular geological zone and crop distribution. The heavy rainfall makes the growing of tree crops like cocoa, rubber, oil palm possible in the rainforest. In the northern region, the crops grown are mainly those which required light rainfall such as rice, millet, cotton and grasses for livestock. Tropical crops grow best in temperatures

between 18⁰–32⁰C. The general high temperatures in Nigeria are favorable to plant growth. Sunlight is important in that it provides the energy required for the photosynthetic activities of the plant. Sunshine hours induce certain physiological processes within the plant for example flowering and ripening. The importance of moisture to crop growth and development can be summarized in terms of the general functions as a major constituent of the living cell itself. Between 85-95% of the weight of most plant tissue is water. Secondly, water serves as a universal solvent, which allows critical biochemical reactions to take place within the plant. Lastly, moisture (water) serves as the solvent through which essential nutrients are carried through the plant and as an important ingredient of photosynthetic actions and reactions.

Risks can be classified as business and financial risks. Business risks are those associated with farming which are independent of the farmer's financial circumstances. Financial risks are the additional risks faced by a farmer who has less than total equity in the farm operations. Availability of loan funds and the costs of credit are some examples of additional financial risk. Business risks for the farm operator can be classified according to their sources; natural risks arise from the uncertainties in the biological, physical, and climatic processes of cash crops production, economic risks associated with price and income, technological risks associated with equipment obsolescence, social risks associated with the deviation of the behaviour of man from the norm and political risks associated with the institutional changes and government (David, 1990). However, the most important risk in cash crops production is the natural risks associated with weather. The shocks as a result of weather variations cause a significant welfare loss of cash crops farmers. Drought, floods, delayed on-set and cessation of rainfall, poor distribution and rain effectiveness, and other inadequacies in rainfall characteristics can result in substantial losses in yield and post harvest losses.

Vulnerability is a shock causing a significant welfare loss, which depends on an exposure to risks. There may be a shock and no vulnerability if there is adequate risk management. Chronic poor could be seen as the very vulnerable, temporary poor as the vulnerable, and the non-poor as non-vulnerable. The poor farmers are the most vulnerable as shocks have strongest welfare consequences. The high vulnerability makes them risk averse and thus unable or unwilling to engage in higher risk or high return activities. A reduction in vulnerability for farmers is therefore both an end and a means of development (Okunmadewa, 2003). Deviations from the usual narrow range of climatic conditions regarding water, light and temperature will lead to sub-optimal performance of the crops and consequently losses in the yield. Flooding from heavy downpour beyond the water retention capacity of the soil may lead to severe damage to the cash crops plantation from erosion, leaching, and land slides. Lightning and thunder associated with heavy rainfall can wreck havoc to the plantations

This study seeks to find out the effect of rainfall and water use on cocoa production in Nigeria. In subsequent sections are presented conceptual framework, methodology, results and discussions, summary and conclusion.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

There are broadly speaking, three ways of establishing whether climate-agriculture relationships are significant (Olaniyan 1981). The first study is the study of the fundamentals of plant-climate relationships, namely, the radiation and moisture balance for various crops in various climatic environments. The climatic control of maize growth in Samaru, Nigeria, was investigated using this approach by Kassam and Kowal (1973).

The second method of determining climate-agriculture relationships is by studying agricultural data and climatic data for a number of places within a given area, for as long a period as consistent records of both agriculture and climate allow, and deducing agroclimatological relationship from analysis of the data. Thus, Adejuwon (1962) correlated annual cocoa production with total rainfall for Western Nigeria for the period 1937-51 while Lyall (1980) correlated barley yield at East Midlands and Scotland separately with different climatic variables.

The third method is that of studying plant-climate relationships under controlled environments. For example, Babalola (1972) varied the soil moisture regime inside a green house with relative humidity averaging 80 per cent and air temperature of 26⁰C to study the effect of different soil moisture status on the root and aerial development of young plants of cocoa, kola and coffee.

The second method, which is based on the analysis of agricultural, and climate data was employed in this study. The empirical reviewed have taken several forms but these could be grouped into two categories. The first category used the regression and correlation analysis between the crop yield and agro climatic variables. A second approach involves the use of Error Correction Model (ECM) in the analysis of agricultural exports.

Akintola (1983), studying the effects of agro climatic factors on some selected food crops such as cowpea, yam, rice and maize in Ibadan. Following his correlation and regression analysis, the responsiveness of each crop yield to specific agro climatic variables (rainfall, temperature, sunshine and humidity) was determined. Based on his findings, it was known that rainfall has statistically significant effect on yields of rice, cowpea and yam. Also it was seen from the study that agro climatic variables such as temperature, and sunshine also had effects on the yields of crops. Adubi (1986), using methods similar to those used by Akintola, found out that rainfall, rainy days and technology have positive effects on the yield of groundnut and cowpea and accounted for 56% and 52% variations in total yields respectively in Oyo State. Total rainfall was said to have a negative effect on yield of yam in all of Oyo, Ogun, Ondo and Bendel States of Nigeria; and also on the yields of cowpea particularly in the last growing month. Aniedu (1987), studying the effects of agro climatic factors on food crops yield in the Eastern ecological agricultural zone of Nigeria (using cassava, yam, maize and rice as study crops) found out that rainfall also had negative effect on cassava in Anambra and Rivers states but a positive effect in Cross Rivers state. Total rainfall, total number of rain days and technological trend were found to have accounted for 34% variation in cassava yield, 59% in yam yield in Rivers State. These studies are relevant to the present study as the effect of agro climatic factors on the yields of crop was established and other factor such as technology was seen to have positive effect on the yield of crops. In the light of this, the present study also considers other variables (producer prices, exchange rate and Gross Domestic product), which also have effect on the crop yields.

In recent times, studies using co integration and error correction approach as method of analysis have grown in the literature. This is attributed to a number of statistically attractive properties it possesses especially when modeling with non-stationary data (Adam 1992). Okoruwa *et al* (2003) examined the determinants of traditional agricultural exports in Nigeria using co integration and error correction approach. The results of the work showed that agricultural commodity exports to the selected countries were influenced by the domestic output, population growth, quantity supplied by competing countries, index of industrial production of importing countries, and time trend. However, the domestic output and population growth rate were the most significant factors influencing agricultural exports in the importing countries. Tijani *et al* (1999) employed co integration and error correction model to estimate export supply function in Nigeria using time series data that span more than three quarters of the 20th century. The results indicate that weather effect is stationary while producer price and hectare planted to cocoa have a long run equilibrium relationship with cocoa export. This findings is significant to the present study as the results established it that producer price has a long run equilibrium relationship with the cocoa export.

METHODOLOGY

This section presents the methodological framework adopted for the study. The subsequent subsections deal with the scope of data collected, nature and sources of data, analytical procedures

Scope, Sources and Nature of Data

The empirical analysis covers the period between 1970 and 2003. Secondary data used for the analysis were obtained from Federal Meteorological Services Publications (various issues), Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) publications, such as Annual Reports and Statements of Accounts, and the Statistical Bulletin

(various issues). Other sources were Federal Office of Statistics (FOS) Annual Abstract of Statistics (various issues), International Financial Statistics Year Book (IFS) (2000; 2001) and Annual Reports of the Federal Ministry of Agriculture (various issues).

Secondary data collected include the average yield of cocoa sourced from Annual Reports of the Federal Ministry of Agriculture; Statistical Bulletin and Federal Office of Statistics (FOS) Annual Abstracts of Statistics. Total rainfall data were collected from Federal Meteorological Services Publications. Similarly data on exchange rate; produce prices and Gross Domestic Product (GDP) were also collected over the period from Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Publications; Statistical Bulletin and International Financial Statistics Year Book.

Analytical Techniques

Several analytical tools were employed to analyze the data. These include, Dickey – Fuller (DF) test and Augmented

Dickey –Fuller (ADF) statistics, Co integration and Error Correction Models (ECM).

Augmented Dickey – Fuller (ADF) Tests

The test for the stationary or order of the integration of the data series and testing for co integration were carried out using Augmented Dickey –Fuller (ADF) tests. ADF test was used because it captures additional dynamic left out by the DF and ensures that the error term is white noise through the inclusion of additional lag length. The test procedure is given by:

$$(1) \Delta X_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 X_{t-1} + \sum bi \Delta X_{t-1} + \epsilon_t$$

The decision rule is that the t-statistics on the coefficient of the variable α_1 , which is expected to be negative, must be significantly different from the critical values for a given sample size, if the null hypothesis is that variable of interest is non-stationary (i.e. it is integral of order one I (1)).

Co integration Tests

After the order of integration of the variables in the model has been ascertained, the next stage is to test co integration. Co integration is a test of stationary of the residuals generated from running a static regression in levels of one or more of the regressor available on the dependent variable.

A two-step procedure of Engle-Granger test was applied to test for the existence of co integration between the yield and independent variables. According to Engle and Granger (1987), detecting co integration between two economic variables X_t and Y_t begins with applying the DF or other unit root tests individually to the variables.

Then the residual

$$(2) \quad U_t = Y_t - KX_t - C \text{ from the regression}$$

$$(3) \quad Y_t = KX_t + C + U_t \quad (C = \text{Constant}) \text{ is examined to see if}$$

it is I (0)

Error Correction Model (ECM)

Error Correction Model (ECM) is an attempt to integrate economic theory useful in characterizing a long-term equilibrium with an observed disequilibrium by building a model that explicitly incorporates behaviour that would restore the equilibrium. The use of the ECM is facilitated when variable are first-differenced stationary and co integrated. The reason for stationarity is to ascertain the order of integration and if not present the number of times a variable has to be differential to make it stationary.

Since the estimation methods such as “least squares” can be applied to time series data only when all the data series are stationary, then the first difference forms should be used if non-stationary variables are to be included in a regression exercise. For example, for a random walk on non-stationary.

Variable X_t ,

$$(4) \quad X_t = X_{t-1} + \epsilon_t \quad \epsilon_t \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$$

the first difference of X_t can be written as

$\Delta X_t = \epsilon_t$, which is by definition a stationary process.

Co integration or ECM is accepted when the residuals from the linear combination of the non-stationary series I (1) are themselves stationary. The acceptance of the ECM indicates that the model is best specified in the first difference of the variables. The ECM framework in essence guarantees the non-loss information from long-term relationships in the first differences.

The ECM is then used to analyze the impulse response of crop yield to a stimulus in the explanatory variables in a dynamic setting. The estimated equation for cocoa as an example is given as follows:

$$(5) \quad a(L)\Delta CYD_t = a_0 + a_1(L)\Delta CEX_t + a_2(L)\Delta CRP_t + a_3(L)\Delta CRP_{t-1} + a_4(L)\Delta CRN_t + a_5(L)\Delta GDP_t + a_6(L)\Delta GDP_{t-1} - a_7ECM_{t-1} + U_t$$

Where:

CYD_t = Yield of Cocoa in time t ('000) tonnes

CEX_t = Official exchange rate in time t.

CRN_t = Rainfall in time t.

CRP_t = Average producer price in time t.

CRP_{t-1} = Average producer price of the previous year.

GDP_t = Gross Domestic Product in time t.

GDP_{t-1} = Gross Domestic Product of the previous year.

$ECM_{(-1)}$ = the error Correction Factor.

U_t = Stochastic Error term assumed to be independently and normally distributed with zero mean and constant variance.

In terms of a priori expectation, rainfall, exchange rate, GDP and producer price are expected to have positive relationship with the yield. While ECM (-1) is expected to have negative signs. The coefficient of the ECM when it is statistically significant gives credence to the existence of co integration.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results and discussion start with the presentation of stationarity test of the variables used for estimation. Following this is a sub-section on the co integration tests and Error Correction Model (ECM) analysis.

Stationary Tests of the Variables used

The order of integration using ADF classes of unit root tests is presented in table 1. In general, the table reveals that all variables are not stationary at their level but become stationary at their level of first difference. For all the variables in level form, the ADF statistics are above the critical values of -2.9750 and -3.5867 for level without trend and level with trend respectively. Thus, the variables are non-stationary in their level form. In the first difference form, however, we can reject the null hypothesis for all variables and this indicates that the variables are (1).

Table 1: Test for Order of Integration using ADF Tests for Cocoa Yield

Variable	Level without trend	Level with trend	First difference without trend	First difference with trend
LnCEX	.72640	1.9317	-3.1778	-4.2832
LnCRN	-2.5414	-2.7484	-3.0980	-4.0706
LnCRP	-1.3219	-2.5350	-3.5287	-4.2279
LnGDP	-.26338	-2.0385	-3.3259	-4.2232
Critical values 95%	-2.9750	-3.5867	-2.9798	-3.5943

Source: *Extracted from Regression result*

Co-integration Tests for Cocoa Yield.

The null hypothesis is that the number of co-integrating vectors is less than or equal to r, where r is 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 or 9. According to the results in Table 2, we can reject the null hypothesis of zero co-integrating vectors at the 95-percent levels. The trace test statistics for r = 4 is 37.9295 which is greater than the critical value. This means that there exist at most five co-integrating vectors.

Table 2: Test for the number of co-integrating vectors for Cocoa Yield.

H ₀	H _a	Test Statistic	95% critical value
r=0	r =1	89.3513	61.2700
r ≤ 1	r = 2	83.7921	55.1400
r ≤ 2	r = 3	55.7109	49.3200
r ≤ 3	r = 4	44.1568	43.6100
r ≤ 4	r = 5	37.9295	37.8600
r ≤ 5	r = 6	30.0136	31.7900
r ≤ 6	r = 7	14.7085	25.4200
r ≤ 7	r = 8	8.9784	19.2200
r ≤ 8	r = 9	5.9289	12.3900

Source: *Extracted from computer print out.*

Error –Correction Model

The results of the ECM in Table 3 shows that the error-correction term has the expected negative sign and statistically significant. All the regressors are statistically significant which is consistent with the validity of an equilibrium relationship among the variables. Lagged quantities of GDP and price have a significant short run dynamic effect on changes in cocoa yield.

Error Correction Model Analysis

The results of the first step of the model are presented in table 4

The coefficient of rainfall, exchange rate, producer price and GDP are found to be positive for cocoa yield. It is expected that increased in the level of this variables would lead to an increase in the yield of cocoa.

In Table 4, the coefficient of determination (R²) of cocoa is 0.5634, thus the independent variables explain 56.3 % of the variations in the dependent variable. Producer price X₂ was significant at 1% while lagged producer price X₂(-1) was significant at 10%. The Error Correction Term, ECM was significant at 1% for the yield. A feedback of 64% was achieved. This confirms that there is a relationship between the yield and producer price, lagged producer price, Gross Domestic Product and exchange rate.

The results revealed that of all the dependent variables considered were the most significant factors influencing the yield of cocoa.

Table 3: ECM Results of cocoa

Regressor	Dependent Variable Cocoa (ΔLnCYD)		
	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-statistic
Constant	-0.028281	0.043283	-0.653402
$\Delta\text{Ln}(\text{CEX})$	-0.115552	0.124320	-0.929471
$\Delta\text{Ln}(\text{CRN})$	0.159185	0.212257	0.749961
$\Delta\text{Ln}(\text{CRP})$	0.212499	0.102447	2.074226
$\Delta\text{Ln}(\text{CRP})^{-1}$	0.106311	0.096289	1.104087
$\Delta\text{Ln}(\text{GDP})$	0.740497	0.580700	1.275180
$\Delta\text{Ln}(\text{GDP})^{-1}$	0.674015	0.459533	1.466740
Ecm^{-1}	-0.662331	0.182375	-0.653402
R^2	0.693040	-	-
Adjusted R^2	0.499171	-	-
S.E of regression	0.187925	-	-
Sum of squared resid	0.671001	-	-
Log likelihood	16.42950	-	-
Durbin _Watson Stat	1.892262	-	-
Mean dependent var	-0.008788	-	-
S.D dependent var	0.265546	-	-
Akaike info criterion	-0.214344	-	-
Schwarz criterion	0.381112	-	-
F-Statistic	3.574778	-	-
Prob (F-Statistic)	0.006581	-	-

Source: *Extracted from computer print out of ECM analysis of cocoa.*

Table 4: Restricted parameter estimate for cocoa

Crop	Constant term	X_2	X_3	$X_{3(-1)}$	X_4	ECM_{-1}	R^2	F	DW	SC
Cocoa	-0.04 (-1.06)	1.39 (2.01)**	0.23 (2.89)*	0.16 (1.98)***	1.11 (2.03)**	0.64 (-3.99)*	0.5634	6.71+	2.53	-0.02

The values in parenthesis are t values

* t values significant at 1%, ** t values significant at 5%, *** t values significant at 10%, +F values significant at 1%, D.W.= Durbin-Watson statistic, Sc= Schwartz information criterion, R^2 = R-squared

Source: Extracted from computer print out.

Policy implications and conclusion

Based on the findings of the study; some important policies for increasing the yield of the crop studied emerged. Rainfall, producer prices, lagged producer prices, exchange rate and GDP were all the important factors that influence the yield of the cocoa. Emerging from this is to formulate adequate global environmental management policy to address the problem of climate change due to global warming. Government should establish an agricultural data base center where all information relating to agriculture can be obtained easily when necessary. This will go a long way to solve the problem of non-available agricultural data and that of inconsistencies in the available ones of which have hampered planning in Nigeria over-time.

Equally there is a need to formulate a policy that would increase the producer prices of cocoa so as to encourage increased in cultivation of cocoa farms, as farmer would be motivated to develop new hectareage for cocoa cultivation and have more money to procure farm inputs such as chemicals. Emerging from the

study is the fact that GDP was one of the key factors that influence the cocoa yield. GDP is partly an element of national income of country. Therefore, in order to boost the production of cocoa there is a need for government to formulate a broad policy that would create enabling environment to produce goods and increased the capacity building of industries especially agro-allied industries that make use of cocoa. Also, there is a need for government to formulate exchange rate policy that would boost agricultural production.

Agricultural industry can only be developed if people are better off to demand products from agro-allied industry such as food and drinks industries that produce beverages, milk and others. This can only be done if government can address the problem of income redistribution that would pay all and sundry in the society.

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